

Reviewer Acknowledgements

International Journal of Statistics and Probability wishes to acknowledge the following individuals for their assistance with peer review of manuscripts for this issue. Their help and contributions in maintaining the quality of the journal is greatly appreciated.

Many authors, regardless of whether *International Journal of Statistics and Probability* publishes their work, appreciate the helpful feedback provided by the reviewers.

Reviewers for Volume 8, Number 1

Abdullah A. Smadi, Yarmouk University, Jordan
Afsin Sahin, Gazi University, Turkey
Ali Reza Fotouhi, University of the Fraser Valley, Canada
Anna Grana, University of Palermo, Italy
Carla J. Thompson, University of West Florida, USA
Felix Almendra-Arao, UPIITA del Instituto Politécnico Nacional, México
Gabriel A. Okyere, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana
Gerardo Febres, Universidad Simón Bolívar, Venezuela
Hui Zhang, St. Jude Children's Research Hospital, USA
Ivair R. Silva, Federal University of Ouro Preto – UFOP, Brazil
Krishna K. Saha, Central Connecticut State University, USA
Man Fung LO, Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong
Olusegun Michael Otunuga, Marshall University, USA
Philip Westgate, University of Kentucky, USA
Qingyang Zhang, University of Arkansas, USA
Sajid Ali, Quaid-i-Azam University, Pakistan
Samir Khaled Safi, The Islamic University of Gaza, Palestine
Shatrunjai Pratap Singh, John Hancock Financial Services, USA
Sohair F. Higazi, University of Tanta, Egypt
Subhradev Sen, Alliance University, India
Vilda Purutcuoglu, Middle East Technical University (METU), Turkey
Vyacheslav Abramov, Swinburne University of Technology, Australia
Wei Zhang, The George Washington University, USA
Weizhong Tian, Eastern New Mexico University, USA
Zaixing Li, China University of Mining and Technology (Beijing), China

Wendy Smith

On behalf of,

The Editorial Board of *International Journal of Statistics and Probability*
Canadian Center of Science and Education